

Technical University of Berlin

Building Sustainability

Paper

Topic: Time Value of Money - Internal Rate of Return

Academic Year: 2021/2022

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Abstract. The Internal Rate of Return is an indispensable tool in financial markets and institutions. The paper is structured in two parts. The first part gives a fuller account and version of Time Value of Money and Internal Rate of Return. The second part revolves around the circumstances and pieces of evidence that contribute to the results of IRR in the Bond Market. To conclude, the paper absorbs the quantitative methods and theory of IRR for different capital and investment-related conundrums. **Keywords.** *Time Value of Money, Net Present Value, Capital Budgeting, Internal Rate of Return, Cost Opportunity, Bond Markets, Interest Rate, Discounting Factor, Cash Flow.*

1. Introduction

This paper explains the Internal Rate of Return (IRR) to understand how finance, savings and investments work. The research re-arranges different results, implications, definitions, methods and problems to expand on the topic of Internal Rate of Return. An experienced researcher, as well as a student new to the topic, would understand why it is important to list arguments, examine and connect points on different complicated relations. As we dive deeper into financial decisions and risks, we substantiate the role of IRR. The paper develops on the definitions of ‘Time Value of Money’, ‘Net Present Value’, ‘Internal Rate of Return’ and ‘Opportunity Cost’ to understand the theory. Quantitative methods and analysis techniques involved in the process of important decisions on investments are based on cash flows. Cash flow, security valuation and descriptive statistics help us forecast the risks.¹ Therefore, the uncertainty involving the returns on investments cannot be ruled out for a fact. However, after examining how lending and borrowing takes place in the financial markets, we can determine and interpret interest rates.² Institutions and individuals make decisions on new investment ideas. This results in a capital budgeting process that stems from analysing proposals, planning budget capital, monitoring and post-budgeting.³ The management of available resources, capital and timing of the cash flows are based on the basic principles of the budgeting

¹ CFA Institute CFA Program: Ethical and Professional Standards And Quantitative Methods, 2020, p.327.

² *ibid* p.330.

³ CFA Institute CFA Program: Corporate Finance and Equity, Volume 4, 2020, Capital Budgeting, p.48.

process. The criteria that analysts use to evaluate capital investments is the focus of this research paper. Whether a project is profitable or not is decided by the analysts after dealing with all the aspects of Net Present Value (NPV) and Internal Rate of Return (IRR).

2. Notations and definitions

(a) Time Value of Money. It is simple to understand that value of money today is worth more than the future value of money. In other words, the future cash flow is worth less than a similar cash flow today.⁴ Therefore, the Time Value of Money is the equivalence relationship between cash flows on different dates.⁵ There are three factors why the value of future cash flow is less than the present value.⁶ First, an individual likes to consume now than to consume it later in the future. Secondly, inflation reduces the future value of the money and so purchasing power of an individual also falls. Thirdly, future cash flow may not be delivered and there is always a risk attached to it. Take this for an example: You give €100 today and get paid €40 in return. Would you consider it? No, you won't. However, if you get €40 today and pay €100 one year later then you can say that there are similarities in values here. Because the value of €100 one year from now would be less to you than the value of €100 today. So it would be fair to discount it to the present value which means to cut its value on how much time passes. Therefore, interest rate or 'r' is the 'rate of return' on future cash flows. Considering the value of €40 as equal to the value of €100 one year from now, we can say that $€100 - €40 = €60$ is the required compensation for getting €100 one year from now. The interest rate here can be, therefore, calculated as the required rate of compensation which is $60/40 = 1.5$ or 150%. Interest rates can be interpreted in three ways – a rate of return, discounting rate and cost of opportunity.⁷

(b) Opportunity Cost and Time Value of Money. As we saw in the earlier example, interest rate and discounting rate are used interchangeably. Because

⁴ CFA Institute CFA Program: Ethical and Professional Standards And Quantitative Methods, 2020, p.314.

⁵ *ibid* p.314.

⁶ A. Damodaran, The Little Book of Valuation, Edition 2011, John Wiley and Sons Inc, Chapter 2, p.17

⁷ CFA Institute CFA Program: Ethical and Professional Standards And Quantitative Methods, 2020, p.330.

the required rate of return, in the beginning, was the interest rate and later we used it to discount the same cash flow in this case. Cost of opportunity can be explained as the value that investors forgo by choosing another course of action.⁸ In the example we showed earlier, if the party that supplied €40 today had decided to rather spend it today, then they would have forgone earning 1.5 or 150% interest rate which is the opportunity cost. Marketplace, therefore, dictates the interest rates based on the supply and demand of lending and borrowing. So, this explains why the opportunity cost concept requires the consideration of the Time Value of Money. Opportunity cost or interest rate dictated by the marketplace can be viewed as a risk-free interest rate plus a set of four premiums to compensate or give required returns for enduring risks.⁹ That is, $r = \text{Real risk-free interest rate} + \text{Inflation premium} + \text{Default risk premium} + \text{Liquidity premium} + \text{Maturity premium}$ (i). The sum of real risk-free interest rate and inflation premium gives us a nominal interest rate. Now that we have understood what Economics says about the Time Value of Money and different meanings of ‘r’ or interest rates, we can, thus, discuss the tools used by analysts to evaluate capital investments.

(c) Net Present Value (NPV). “For a disbursement of one investment by a project, the net present value is the present value of the future after-tax cash flows minus the investment outlay”.¹⁰ $NPV = \sum_{t=1}^n CF_t / (1+r)^t - \text{Outlay}$ (ii); where, ‘ CF_t ’ is after-tax cash flow after time t, ‘r’ is required rate of return for the investment and ‘Outlay’ is investment cash flow at time zero. To understand the criterion, let’s take an example: Consider a Playing Cards Company is making an investment of €10 million in a project that has a cash flow of €3.2 million after-tax per year for the next four years plus another €4 million in Year 6. The required rate of return is 8%. For that Playing Cards Company; $NPV = 3.2 / (1+0.08)^1 + 3.2 / (1+0.08)^2 + 3.2 / (1+0.08)^3 + 3.2 / (1+0.08)^4 + 3.2 / (1+0.08)^5 + 4 / (1+0.08)^6 - 10$; $NPV = 15.28 - 10$; therefore, $NPV = €5.3 \text{ million}$. From this example, one can understand that the company’s total value or present value of the future cash flow is €15.28 million. This investment will

⁸ CFA Institute CFA Program: Ethical and Professional Standards And Quantitative Methods, 2020, p.330.

⁹ *ibid.* p.330.

¹⁰ CFA Institute CFA Program: Corporate Finance and Equity, Volume 4, 2020, Capital Budgeting, p.52.

be acquired by the company after giving up its wealth that's worth €10 million today and enduring risks with a return on investments of 8%. Meaning the wealth increased by €5.3 million in the future and that is NPV. Since NPV helps the investor to decide whether to go for the investment or not, it can be summarized as 'Invest' if $NPV < 0$ or 'Don't Invest' if $NPV > 0$.¹¹

(d) Internal Rate of Return (IRR). “For a disbursement of one investment by a project, the IRR is the discount rate that makes the present value of the future after-tax cash flows equal that investment's disbursement.”¹² In investment mathematics this can be expressed as $\sum_{t=1}^n CF_t / (1+IRR)^t - Outlay = 0$ OR $\sum_{t=1}^n CF_t / (1+IRR)^t = Outlay$ (iii); so if we look at it closely, the equation looks like NPV except that here 'r' or discounting rate is IRR (instead of the required rate of return). In the Playing Cards Company's example, we want to calculate such that the present net value of the after-tax cash flows equals zero. In equation form; $-10 + 3.2 / (1+IRR)^1 + 3.2 / (1+IRR)^2 + 3.2 / (1+IRR)^3 + 3.2 / (1+IRR)^4 + 3.2 / (1+IRR)^5 + 4 / (1+IRR)^6 = 0$; algebraically, this is very difficult to solve. Manually, one would do the trial and error method by systematically selecting the different discount rates to find the correct IRR that fulfils the equation. In the previous example, we discounted the cash flows at 8% and found NPV to be €5.3 million. Since NPV is positive it is safe to assume that IRR is greater than 8%. However, should we assume an IRR of say, 20%, then the NPV becomes -€1.17 million. It is with trial and error one can find the IRR that satisfies the equation and equals zero. Additionally, expert researchers substantiate the fact that IRR is independent of the Cost of Capital.¹³ It means that IRR is different from the required rate of return in financial markets. Therefore, IRR can be interpreted as “the rate of return of an asset whose capital growth is time invariant and whose cash flows mimic the project's cash flows. Simply put, it is the rate of return a project would have if the capital grew at a constant pace.”¹⁴ In the second part of the research paper, we will examine investment-related mathematical problems revolving around IRR.

¹¹ CFA Institute CFA Program: Corporate Finance and Equity, Volume 4, 2020, Capital Budgeting, p.53.

¹² *ibid.* p.53.

¹³ C.A. Magni, Investment Decisions and the Logic of Valuation, Springer Nature Switzerland AG, 2020.

¹⁴ *Ibid.*

(e) Bond Markets and Internal Rate of Return. When a company decides to expand or to invest in new products, it needs funds for the next investment. This need for new funds results in the issuance of new bonds. A bond is nothing but a “certificate of indebtedness” that specifies the indebtedness of the borrower to the buyer of the bond or the lender.¹⁵ Bonds come with a date of maturity which specifies the time at which the loan will be repaid and the rate of interest that borrower promises to pay from time to time until the bond matures. It is, therefore, necessary to examine how different bonds have different IRR or yields. There are four factors or categories that influence a bond and its IRR. The first is the bond’s duration or length of time.¹⁶ These bonds are either long-term or short-term bonds in terms of their date of maturity. IRR of the bond depends on its term. Long-term bonds are riskier than short-term bonds because the lender has more wait longer for the repayment of the principal. If the holder decides to sell the bond before the date of maturity, then that holder has to sell it at a lower price. To compensate for this risk, long-term bonds come with higher interest rates than short-term bonds. The second factor that influences the IRR of the bond is credit-risk.¹⁷ Credit-risk means that there are chances that a borrower might default in payment of interest rates or the principal amount. When borrowers perceive the credit-risk with a high probability for their bonds, there is a demand for higher interest rates or compensation for these risks. These credit-risks are ranked by financial rating institutions. The higher the risk, the higher is the yield and vice-a-versa. The third factor or characteristic of a bond is tax treatment.¹⁸ Different taxes treat the returns earned from the interest rate differential. Returns earned from the bonds are taxable so, the owner of the bond has to pay the taxes. However, bonds issued by the state or government is not taxable. Therefore, different bonds issued by different governments or corporate companies have different interest rates. The interest rates are lower for the bonds issued by the government. And finally, the fourth factor is inflation protection.¹⁹ These bonds factor the interest rates to the measure of inflation to compensate for the fall in the purchasing power of the money.

¹⁵ Mankiw, Principles of Economics, Edition 2019, p.609.

¹⁶ *ibid.* p. 610.

¹⁷ *ibid.*

¹⁸ *ibid.*

¹⁹ *ibid.*

(f) Negative Yields on Bonds. In Europe, Sweden and Denmark have negative interest rates. To understand this it is necessary to examine the role a monetary policy plays in an economy. The central bank has target inflation of 2% to 3%. But when interest rates are lower, credit is available in the market and consumers have more purchasing power. This induces a rise in demand and results in an increase in prices of the goods and services. Eventually, consumers start borrowing from tomorrow's earnings at a higher rate because credit is cheap and there is a steady rise in salaries. This results in unhealthy inflation, a rise in prices and the purchasing power of the currency drops. To tackle this inflation, later, central banks and financial institutions step in and increase the interest rates. But now deflation takes place due to high-interest rates and prices drop dramatically because consumers start keeping their money to themselves and nobody is investing. Deflation is not welcome here, so the other alternative central banks have is to lower the interest rates even further after deflation and make the interest rates negative. This floods the economy with money and yields on the bonds become negative as well. It is this scenario that leads to speculation on the currency. Later, in the long run, the currency of that country will become stronger than US Dollars. And that will compensate for the current negative yields on the bonds.

3. Investment mathematics of IRR related problems

Example A. Consider this example to understand the interpretation of IRR from mathematical data. There is project A that made an investment of €2.5 million in the year 2021. The NPV of the future cash flows in the year 2027 for this project is €8.71.410. While NPV of the cash flow after one year is €2.80.652. The IRR for the project is 6.9%. In similar terms, there is project B, made an investment of €2.5 million in the year 2021. And NPV of the future cash flows in the year 2027 is €4.10.900; while NPV of the cash flow after one year is €6.40.527. IRR for this project is 9.3%. Which project is more profitable? The answer, project B because it has a higher IRR. However, it is important to note that we don't have NPV of the entire project so that's why we should assume that project B is better than project A based on IRR. (See Exhibit 1)

Example B. There is a bond at a market price of €107,3. The par value is 100 and the coupon rate is 3.5% while the yield is 1.6%. This means that the bond is

credit-risk free and safer in the market. That's why it has a higher interest rate, lower yield while there is a higher market price for the bond. The yield here is calculated based on the model of IRR. (See Exhibit 2)

4. Conclusion. Higher the IRR, better the project, however, one must note that if NPV and other quantitative tools are available, the profitability of the investments is influenced by these factors. In Bond Markets, the lower the yield is and the higher the interest rates are, the safer is the bond. However, negative yield means that there is speculation on the rise in the purchasing power of the currency. And that will compensate for the negative yields in the long run. IRR is an indispensable tool in the financial markets.

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Appendix

Exhibit 1

IRR Project A	6.9%
IRR Project B	9.3%

Year	Cash Flow Years	Expected Cash flow from Project A	Expected Cash flow from Project B	Discounting factor Project A	Discounting factor Project B	PV Net Cash Flows Project A	PV Net Cash Flows Project B
2021	0	-25,00,000	-25,00,000			-25,00,000	-25,00,000
2022	1	3,00,000	7,00,000	0.9355	0.9150	2,80,652	6,40,527
2023	2	3,50,000	7,00,000	0.8752	0.8373	3,06,310	5,86,107
2024	3	5,00,000	6,00,000	0.8187	0.7662	4,09,364	4,59,695
2025	4	4,70,000	3,00,000	0.7659	0.7011	3,59,985	2,10,320
2026	5	3,80,000	3,00,000	0.7165	0.6415	2,72,280	1,92,451
2027	6	13,00,000	7,00,000	0.6703	0.5870	8,71,410	4,10,900
Net Cash Flow						0	0

Exhibit 2

Input Table	
Current Market Price	107.3
Par Value	100
Yield	1.6%
Coupon rate	3.5%

Particulars	Nov-22	Nov-23	Nov-24	Nov-25
Year	1.0	2.0	3.0	4.0
Coupon	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5
Principal repayment				100
Total cashflow	3.5	3.5	3.5	103.5
Discounting factor	0.9842	0.9687	0.9535	0.9384
PV of cashflows	3.4	3.4	3.3	97.1
Current market price	107.3			